

Magnetic properties of aluminum doped Barium Hexagonal Ferrite

Shalini Govindaraj M, Subha A, Arigsh.V, Subasa C. Sahoo*

Department of Physics, Central University of Kerala, Kasargod - 671314, Kerala

Email: *Email: subasa@cukerala.ac.in

Abstract

BaAlFe₁₁O₁₉ nanoparticles were synthesized by modified sol gel autocombustion method and were subsequently annealed at different temperatures. Structural studies showed the presence of single phase BaAlFe₁₂O₁₉ in the samples annealed at and above 900°C. The average grain size was found to be increased after annealing. The spontaneous magnetization (M_s) value shows systematic variation with the increase in annealing temperature. Maximum values of 71 and 109 emu/g were observed at 300K and 60K respectively for the sample annealed at 1200°C. A maximum coercivity of 6696Oe was observed at 300K for the sample annealed at 1100 °C. Magnetization was increased at 60 K compared to that at 300 K whereas the coercivity decreased for all the annealed samples at 60 K. The observed magnetization behaviour in these nanoparticle samples may be explained on the basis of grain growth, canting of moments, modified exchange interactions in the lattice.

Fig.1. a) XRD patterns of the BaF-Asp and samples annealed at different temperatures b) Typical M-H loops of the T_A-

1000 sample at 300K and 60K.

Keywords: sol gel autocombustion, exchange interactions and canting.